

**THE ROLE OF VISUALIZATION TOOLS IN THE ANALYSIS OF NAVOI
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This article describes how to effectively analyze Navoi gazelles using new pedagogical technologies when teaching in educational institutions. An analysis of Alisher Navoi's work mentions all the elements associated with the use of words in prose and lyric works. At the same time, we are talking about some methods. Information will also be provided on the analysis of events, its linguistic ethics and elements that should be paid attention to when analyzing the text.

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Analysis and interpretation of a work of art is one of the eternal mummo of literary studies. Even the most famous writers, devout literary critics, recognize objective and subjective point of view in this regard. Analysis is understood as the separation of the artistic text into the corresponding parts in the process of a person's cognitive activity, as well as the identification of the peculiarities of the connections between them.

As you know, any artistic text (of course, the sentence goes only on texts that can answer students of high artistry) will concentrate a certain amount of information. The Zamir of this information contains not only the content of the message, notification, but also aspects that affect the human psyche. That is why the creators think extremely seriously over every word when creating each work (so to speak, composing an artistic text).

Nevertheless, the same answer cannot be given to the question of how to analyze a work of art. This is influenced by many factors, such as the goals and objectives of the analysis, who analyzes it and for whom it is analyzed, the period of creation of the artistic text, its author, purpose, genre, style, form.

Fiction as a holistic whole. It is a saying that any whole consists of its own pieces, small pieces. The work of art also has its own fragments, parts and directions as such integrity. Only this integrity

and its structural elements do not easily stand out as much as the composition of material bodies and its parts. Its structure and composition have much more complexities. If we take a car, tool or object, it will be possible to imagine its integrity and parts relatively easily. For example, let's take a children's toy car or Apple. There is an external part of the car, wheels, an axis that holds them, a "motorch" that drives the car. They can be separated and reassembled separately. A good example in this regard is kinder, which serves as a dessert and toy for children. It is a monolithic single toy, consisting of separate parts. It is from this combination of integrity that a toy is formed that gives the child's heart a touch. Apples also have their own components as a holistic body. Now its composition will consist of other parts. It stands out in appearance, shape, taste, color. But all the elements that provide its flavor and color are not visible to the eye. We can emotionally perceive the presence of various chemists and microelements in it, the formation of this taste and color as a result of their general combination. It is also worth noting that for a person eating an apple, such a composition of it is absolutely not interesting. Special attention can be paid to its composition only when the physician's recommendation is necessary.

A similar work of fiction also has a number of internal divisions, components, whose interconnections are difficult to progress at once. But it would not be correct to say that these links are random as well as irregular. In their connections there is a certain consistency, order, that is, specific laws.

Therefore, a work of art is an integrity consisting of extremely complex connections of individual parts subject to specific laws. And in order to fully understand the essence of this state, the need arises to imagine the internal structure of the work. It turns out that by itself it is necessary to cut those parts of it into small pieces, to find out the features of the connections between them.

But there is no harm to the product itself from separating or combining the children's toy or parts in the "kinder". It can be bottled again or disassembled. What if a mechanical approach to a work of art also occurs in this way?! In it, we remain without realizing, without feeling the true essence of a work of art, the artistic charm embodied in it.

Usually, not a single excess element is present in a perfect work of art. Even each sound is distinguished by the fact that it fulfills the corresponding artistic and aesthetic tasks. We can find as much as we want evidence relevant to this thesis in the process of reading classical works.

Mengizlari gul-gul, mijjalari xor,
Qaboqlari keng-keng, og'izlari tor.

In this verse, in addition to the general meaning of the poem, it can be seen that each word involved in it (even some derived sounds) is of particular note. The purpose of the poem (poet – Alisher Navoi) is to describe and describe the beauty of the garden. For this, its appearance was selected. In this, basically, the face (cornea), eyelashes (mija), between the eyes and eyebrows (scabbard) and mouth are taken to the pencil. To accomplish the goal, however, the use of the appropriate vocabulary was lacking for the poet, who also felt the need for repeated use of certain words (flower-flower, wide-wide). Not today, it emphasizes the purposeful repetition of certain sounds as well. It is not for nothing that the plural suffix –s is repeated four times. As a result, the tone level of the poem was greatly increased.

Another of the elements that ensure an increase in tonality is associated with the construction of a sentence. Four rhythmic pieces in it can be distinguished. It is possible for us to imagine this more closely if we put the verses in series in equal parts:

Mengizlari gul-gul, mijjalari xor,
Qaboqlari keng-keng, og'izlari tor.

In this, it can be seen that words in odd and even rows have mutually proportional rhythmic positions. We are not talking about the role and significance of other image media in the verses. Whereas the tashbih used in it (mengizi – flower-flower; mijjalari – chorus), the epithet (wide-wide; narrow) are also distinguished by their freshness and likability. All this, combined, brings to the surface the artistic-aesthetic effect that the poem can exert on the reader (reader).

So, in the analysis of a work of art, approaching it as a holistic phenomenon allows you to cover all the educational and aesthetic aspects that the artistic text Envisions at a relatively wider level. And one of the main results of this, we will be able to observe in the maturation of skills and qualifications related to the formation of the artistic and aesthetic taste of the reader. After all, "a holistic analysis of the text is a kind of work in which a functional and systematic approach to the study of language is realized, and inter – subject communication is vividly manifested." In addition, it can be said that such an analysis of an artistic text leads to a more thoughtful progression of its essence as a literary phenomenon.

We can observe a ghazal analysis as an experiment:

Mehr ko'p ko'rguzdim, ammo mehribone topmadim.
Jon base qildim fido, oromi jone topmadim.

G'am bila jonimg'a ettim g'amgusore ko'rmadim,
 Hajr ila dilxasta bo'ldum, dilsitone topmadim.
 Ishq aro yuz ming malomat o'qiga bo'ldim nishon,
 Bir kamonabro'da tuzluqdin nishone topmadim.
 Ko'nqlum ichra sarv o'qdur, g'uncha paykon, gul tikan,
 Dahr bog'i ichra mundog' gulsitone topmadim.
 Husn mulki ichra sendek, shohi zolim ko'rmadim,
 Ishq ko'yida o'zumdek notavone topmadim.
 Ko'p o'qudim Vomiqu Farhodu Majnun qissasin,
 O'z ishimdin bul'ajabroq dostone topmadim.
 Ul amon ichinda bo'lsun, ey Navoiy, garchi men,
 Bir zamon ishqida mehnatdin amone topmadim.
 Tab' ganjiddin maoniy xurdasin yuz qatla hayf,
 Kim, nisor etmakka shohi xurdadone topmadim.

Despite the fact that the topic of *ishq* is the main one in *ghazal*, socio-philosophical content also occupies a significant place in it. The lyrical hero gives his affection to those around him, insisting that the process of showing affection is long and continuous ("much"). He is even willing to sacrifice his life. In return, he sees only a lack of affection, does not find a loving, suicidal person. This "introduction" in *ghazal* is characterized by having a generalization property. New words are made here with the participation of the words "love" and "soul", which attract attention with their new meanings.

In the next byte, some aspects of this generality will seem to open:

G'am bila jonimg'a yettim g'amgusore ko'rmadim,
 Hajr ila dilxasta bo'ldum, dilsitone topmadim.

Now the lyrical Hero claims to be grieving, tormented and tormented ("got to my soul"), but does not find a "caring", that is, a caring, caring person. In *Hajr*, i.e., *ayriliq*, his *dili* becomes "sick" – ill ("dilkhasta" means despondent, *dili* means ruin). And the one who is going to be an ointment for this ailment is nowhere ("dilsiton" has the connoisseur of the heart, Captivator of the heart, charming meanings). The discovery of new meanings through the use of First-Byte pronouns continues in this byte as well: "Grief", "Grief"; "dilkhasta", "dilsiton" fulfills this function.

In both bytes, the image of the state at two opposite poles is the main place. While the first pole shows a man who shows affection, gives his life, lives in sorrow and sorrow, and from Hajr dili ozur, the second pole stands a kind of drawing of those who are careless and clumsy towards those who live in these afflictions, unable to share grief, unable to hunt for pleasure.

In the third verse, a clearer picture of the anguish given in the initial general way becomes visible:

Ishq aro yuz ming malomat o'qiga bo'ldim nishon,
Bir kamonabro'da tuzluqdin nishone topmadim.

Now it is revealed that the cause of these anguish is ishq. The above logical contradiction continues here as well. The "hundred thousand" in the first stanza (which can also be read in the hundred, thousand style) has the meanings of "many", "many" in a portable sense. In this sense, it can contrast with the word "one" in the next stanza. Because in this place, "one", in addition to the meaning "only one", also has the meanings "little", "little", "no". "Kamonabro" and "tuzluk" are also contradictory in meaning. The first word means "like a bow". It becomes self-evident that the bow is chosen as meaningful in contrast to "tuzluk", the word for "straightness".

Gulistan is known for its trees (Cypress), flowers (buds) and thorns. And the poet likens his heart to that Gulistan:

Ko'nglum ichra sarv o'qdur, g'uncha paykon, gul tikan,
Dahr bog'i ichra mundog' gulsitone topmadim.

Only the Sarv in this is replaced by an arrow, the gun is replaced by a Pike of the same arrow, that is, a metal spike at the tip of the arrow, and the flower is replaced by a spike. The use of proper pronouns in the pattern of "flower", "gulsiton" continued here as well.

If attention is paid, from the first verse of the ghazal, a conflict is placed between the "I" - speaker and the others. Attention is drawn to the confrontation between me and others. This is the first person to show affection in the initial verse, and those who are misplaced with it, the lyrical hero grieving in the second verse, and the frivolous to him, the lover who is giriftor of love in the third verse, and the "archonabro" who does not treat him properly. Such a contradiction in the fourth stanza can be seen between the love heart and the "garden of genius".

Logical countermeasures continue in the next byte. Here it was realized between the "tyrant of the King" (sen) and the "notavon" (I). The "tyrant of the king" is in the husn estate, and the "notavon" is in the "lightsaber". It will not be difficult for us to even advance the conflict between spatial meanings if we mean that the word "koi" also has the meaning of "neighborhood", "village".

Finding a meaningful contradiction in the next byte is a little more complicated. Where the dictionary units meaning contradiction are not explicitly given:

Ko'p o'qudum Vomiqu Farhodu Majnun qissasin,
O'z ishimdin bul ajabroq dostone topmadim

In fact, content meant "a lot" and "no" was to be expected from the meaning of the byte. The same content is available. Only in its lexical expression is originality observed. With a lot of reading (in any of them), the words that I did not find perform this function. The conflict in the style of me and others also continued. Here, the words of Vomiqu Farhodu Majnun form the pole of" they "and the pole of" own "form the pole of" I".

In the next byte, the logical contradiction came openly: in the form of ul and I. The art of using consonants interrupted in the previous two bytes (amon, amone) is continued here again. Unlike other ghazals of the Nawab, in this ghazal the pseudonym is not quoted in the last verse, but in a single preceding verse from it. In the final verse of the ghazal, the content is again turned towards social tones. It is worth noting that the mention, description of philosophical, socio-political, moral-educational issues in the Treasury has reached a completely new level in Navoi's work.

This gazel is written in the mahzuf weight of ramali musamma of aruz. We can describe it as follows:

Meh r ko'p ko'r guz di mam mo meh ri bo ne top ma dim.
- V - - - V - - - V - - - V -
Jon ba se qil dim fi do o ro mi jo ne top ma dim
- V - - - V - - - V - - - V -

Babur describes Ramal as the most common weight in his work" Mukhtasar", and mentions that Navoi's poems in Ramal are much larger than those he wrote in all other weights. It also notes that all ghazals of Husayn Boyqara are written only at this weight.

Now we can have some practical recommendations on the question of what should be paid more attention to when performing a linguistic analysis of a holistic artistic text. In our eyes, it will be advisable to pay more attention to the following elements in this:

1. Expressive reading of the text and determining the meaning and content of each word in it.
2. Identifying a system of base words in a text (even each byte or clause, abzas).
3. An attempt to find aspects of the text that are relevant to the author's bevoisita personality.
4. Determining which of the types of speech (description, definition, story, reasoning)the text

belongs to, determining which genre it belongs to, proving the signs of the genre (holistic text, epzod, Ghazal, ruboi) based on the materials of the text.

5. Structure of the text, identification of its composition, determination of the scope of the topic.
6. If the text does not have a title, it is possible to find a suitable title for it (this work can also be applied to each byte of the Treasury) and interpret it.
7. Dividing the text into the corresponding logical parts, drawing up its compact plan and identifying the connections between these parts, paying attention to the formative indicators of these links.
8. Focusing on the peculiarities of the beginning and end of the text, the connections between them, the types of image tools in it, the study of their artistic and aesthetic functions.
9. Determination of the specifics of the priority methods in the construction of the text (comparison, opposition, evolutionary evolution or faster exchange of emotions).
10. Clarification of the features of the poetic work regarding the rhyme system, weight, band structure.
11. The main image in the text (for example, a lyrical hero, lover, mistress, rival ...) to give a description of the.
12. To determine the linguistic features of the text (meaning unfamiliar or annotated words, contextual synonyms in the text, words reflecting logical contradiction, plural words, colloquial words, new words, vernacular expressions and phrases, goals and objectives foreseen from their use).
13. Observation of the phonetic construction of the text and its specifics. In this, pay attention to the manifestation of the author's skill.
14. Determination of the nature of morphological (to the use of words and suffixes, in the making of new words) identities in the text.
15. Identification of the peculiarities of poetic syncytics (inversion, elements inherent in oral speech, hero and author's speech), assessment of the degree of harmony of the relations of form and meaning in the text.
16. Mark the skill of the author and express a personal attitude and assessment towards the text.

Of course, it is difficult to do all this at once within the framework of the analysis of one work. Nevertheless, there is no doubt that paying attention to them will help to reveal the meaning and essence of a work of art, its initial path wider in imagining internal possibilities.

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